

ACCESS TO TOURISM INFORMATION AMONG UNIVERSITY ACADEMIC STAFF

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Abstract:

Tourism involve temporary movement from place of residence to a destination for the purpose of rest and relaxation, recreation, sightseeing, education (viewing of nature for knowledge and conservation), visiting friends and relatives, business, medical treatments, pilgrimages and attendance at religious festivals, exhibitions and conventions attending sporting events and holidaying from work. On the other hand tourism information is the information that enables a potential tourist to access the destination of interest, insight of information about attraction and destination Survey research method was adopted for the study; the population of this study consists of 600 academic staff from three faculties. A stratified sampling technique was used to select one hundred and eighty (180) 30% respondent that formed the strata with 18 respondents from each stratum. A close-ended questionnaire was design and validated by three lecturers in the department of geography of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria Pre-test and post-test of the instrument was done with 20 academic staff in the department of computer science, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria to ascertain the reliability of the instrument Cronbach Alpha coefficient was used at 0.05 level of significance and was found to be consistent at 0.75. Descriptive statistics of frequency distribution and simple percentages were used in the analysis. Findings of this study, shows that access to tourism information will lead to arousal of interest to participate in tourism activities which is very necessary in planning of itinerary, furthermore tourism has been noted to be a social therapy to stress and boredom. The study recommends that information on all types of tourism products and services should be provided and made available for academics staff and public accesses. Necessary infrastructure should be provided and make available in order to enhance information accesses.

Keywords: tourism, access & information, health & promotion

Introduction

The emergence of tourism as a major industry is one of the most remarkable change that have taken place in the economic activity in the post-world war era. The industry has grown from being a marginal aspect of national economic life to an important socio-economic asset since in the late 1970s. Tourism is of two category; domestic (internal) and international tourism, it can be further classify to; historical/archaeological, eco-tourism, educational, business, culture, religion, safari, environmental, youth and adult, recreation and hospitality. Tourism service and products are based on confidence, information and communication; Information as a life blood of the industry. Without it, the industry cannot function effectively. Before tourist can embark on a trip, they need information in other to plan and choose between options. They also need information as the trip progresses since annual holidays or even the weekend breaks are increasing associated with enormous financial and emotional risks. Werther and Klein reported that many tourist their annual holidays represent a major emotional investment that cannot easily be replaced if some goes wrong therefore, since travellers cannot pre-test the product or easily get their money back if the trip does not measure up to their expectations, access to accurate, reliable, timely and relevant information is essential to help them make appropriate choices. Tourism products are not manufactured goods; most of the products are in service form. However, there are two types of tourism products which are; natural and anthropogenic products.

The natural products are mountains, valleys, rivers, waterfalls, fisheries, and the biogenic products like vegetation in a natural era. The anthropogenic products are the resources created by the activities of man such as; architectural and ethnographical sites (e.g) place of conserved artefacts, historical and archaeological sites such as ruined settlement, sports and religion and cult site. In addition, the service products according to Kolawole (2010) are; Restaurant and catering services, hotel accommodation services, souvenirs, National park service, transports and car hire services, craft ship, textile, travel agencies services and some departmental stores services and ancillaries such as bureau de change services, curries services, insurance and cruise. Therefore consumers seek more and more information about the product before purchase hence the product are fixed geographically that means consumers must travel and in effect before they can consume the product they are buying.

The mass tourism that exists in many parts of the world today has its origins in the years immediately following the conclusion of the 1039-45 second world war. Rising standards of living, increased leisure time and developments in transportation resulted in a sharp increase in demand for international travel, which has grown steadily to the present day. Tourist destinations responded to this demand by developing a wide

variety of tourist facilities and amenities. The origins of tourism can, however, be traced back much further than this to the origin of man, when man was created and put in a garden and he have to move around and watch the beauty of nature (Holy Bible: GEN. 3 vs8). During the early Egyptian when there was a limited amount of travel associated with festivals and celebrations of a religious or spiritual nature. They early Egyptian civilization displayed a primitive social structure that rewarded the privileged classes with leisure time to enjoy such activities as dance, music, drama and archery. Travel in Egyptian tended to be for the purpose of trade or associated with religious activities. In Nigeria the birth of tourism, come to light in 1960 when Nigeria got her independent with the flow of tourism of different kinds into the country. However, this manifested early in 1962 when the Nigeria Tourist Association (NTA) was formed as semi-public sector having direct participation in the formulation of government policies on tourism.

The association had its members coming from the federal government; shell oil, Tobbaco Company, private hoteliers, airport hotels, some foreign airlines and the national carries. In 1990; the then vice president Augustus Aikhomu reviewed the board at Eko Holiday Inn. However, in 1992, decree 81 of December was promulgated to give birth to the Nigeria Tourism Development Corporation (NTDC). Through this decree, every state in Nigeria was required to form Tourism Board at the state and Tourism committee at Local Government level. In 2004, the National Assembly re-affirmed this through an act of the parliament and its amendments. The development of tourism in the country helps to attract large numbers of potential domestic and international customers. It is widely recognized that a profile tourist business demands through planning and understanding of what the potential tourists want. Also, the various arms of government, the public and the parastatals need a better understanding of the essence of tourism and its potential as a revenue generator. Tourism is new to many in this country of ours hence, the underestimation of its importance as a source of revenue. However, locating and developing tourist resources take considerable planning and foresight that only those who are knowledgeable are able to impart. Nigeria is blessed with tourist attraction no doubt. Some of the notable tourist centres in Nigeria includes:

- Abia state: National war museum;
- Akwa Iborn state: Azurnini blue river;
- Anambra state: Juju shrine arochukeu;
- Benue state: Bassa hills, J.S. Tarkar Tourists Park, Katsina-Ala picnic resorts, and Mambilla waterfalls in Oju;
- Bauchi state: Yankari National Park, wiki warn springs;
- Borno state: Chad Basin National park
- Cross River state: Agbokin waterfalls, Obudu Cattle Ranch, Tinapa resort, Cross River National Park.

- Delta state: Abraka river resort, Bible she, Araya
- Edo state: Okomu Wildlife Park, Nana palace, Ososo tourist centre
- Enugu state: Eeagu tourist complex, Silicon hill;
- Imo state: Oqwugwu (forest God), Oguta lake holiday complex, Mbari cultural centres
- Jigawa state: Birnin Kudu Rock painting;
- Kaduna state: Kamuka National park, Terra cotta Nok village, Zaria town walls
- Kano state: Belgore forest, City walls, Gidan dan Hausa, Dyeing pits;
- Kwara state: Pategi beach, Owu waterfalls, Awon mass wedding: Mongo park Tomb jebba dam;
- Kebbi state: Argungu fishing festival;
- Nasarawa state: Maiyegun beach, bar beach, Eyo festival;
- Niger state: Kainji lake National park, Zuma rock, Gurara waterfalls, Bida brass works, Ladi kwali pottery centre, Kainji hydropower-electricity dam, Gani international festival Borgu;
- Ogun state: Oluma rock tourist centre Abeokuta;
- Ondo state: Idanre hills, Ikogosi warm and cold spring;
- Osun state: Birikisu sungbo shrine, Oshogbo holls, Opa oranmiyan, Osun Oshogbo;
- Oyo state: Ibadan University zoological garden, Birikisu sungo shirne;
- Plateau state: Jos Wildlife Park;
- Taraba state: Gashaka-gumpti National Park, Chappal waddi hill, etc.

Statement of the Problem

Access to information is the act of having information in whatever format that can be useful to an individual lives. Therefore, access to tourism information is a process of seeking and obtaining information that will lead a potential tourist to her/his destination. Access to information is very important for human development, education, lives improvement, physical wellbeing and mental alertness; as human beings, we want to be informed, keep abreast of the latest event that affects, or are of interest to us. In the same vein, academics need information on leisure, recreation and tourism, they wants to know the latest football scores, a very legislation that affects their lives, economic activities that affects their daily living to be a part-taker. Furthermore, academics need information on leisure and recreation, activities of our operators and transportation sectors, natural recreation centre or site, e.g (National parks), hotel and accommodations, religion, historical site, sport and events and world around them. This will enable the academics to develop interest and be full participant

of the activities. WHO (2013) said that participation in tourism through physical activities like sports and other recreation help to build and maintain healthy bones, muscles and joints, intellectual balance, reduce fat, control body weight and develop efficient functioning of the hearts and lungs.

Participation in tourism activities make one fit, gives participant more energy, greater mental alertness, reduces stress and allows for better time management and power to create social cohesion productivity. Health is wealth, when you have good health you save a lot of resource. Tourism is life, when you participate in leisure, recreation through exercise, it elongates one's life, it reduces one's body weight, it enhances youthful appearance and also it burn out calories in human system and pave way for adequate functioning of heart.

Alagba (2012) observed that from history the ancient Greeks (where education took its roots) believed that the main idea of educating a man was to produce an individual that would be mentally and physically balanced. According to him the Greeks believed that regular physical exercise through recreation, are not only necessary for the development and maintenance of optimal level of health, but is also contributes to youthful appearance, increase in physical work capacity and decrease early disability and sudden death. He further stressed that access to necessary tourism information by academic staff is in order to enhance their mental relieves. The importance of this is for body refreshment, boredom therapy, increase productivities and long life span. Leisure, recreation and tourism are the largest industry in the world; the business is booming and growing rapidly. Tourism through recreation has a wide range of positive impacts range from cognitive, economic, social, culture, environmental and physiological. People who frequently take advantage of recreation activities have doctor less visits, low body mass indexes and lower symbolic blood pressure (BP) than those who do not.

Kolawole (2010) stated that non participation in tourism activities like leisure and recreation can lead to fatigue, stress and subsequently death. Despite the health value of tourism, it is sad to note that today many academics slumps on their official seat and died due to fatigue and stress related illness like hypertension, heart failure, cardiac arrest and stroke.

According to Triantoro (2013) posits that stressful condition experience by academics staff increases their distress and vulnerability to psychological and behavioural problems such as depressions, fatigue, low productivity, absenteeism and several health problems. In view of the above observed problems, this study investigates type, source and means of accessing tourism information among academics staff of Bayero University Kano, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study sought to provide answers to the following research questions:

1. *What types of tourism information are available to the academics staff?*
2. *What are the means of access to tourism information among academics staff?*
3. *What are source of tourism information among the academics staff?*
4. *What are the challenges faced by the academics staff?*

Objective of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

- a. To identify the types of tourism information available among the academics staff in Bayero University, Kano Nigeria
- b. To find out the sources of tourism information among the academics staff in Bayero University Kano, Nigeria
- c. To examine the means of access to tourism information among academics staff in Bayero University Kano, Nigeria

Significance of the Study

This study will be significant to the following; Academics staff, Stakeholders in tourism industries and members of the society. One of the reasons for undertaking education research is help find solutions to already identified problems for the society to progress. The research findings will provide immense contribution and serve as an eye opener to the members of academic staff on the need to participate in tourism activities. Also, the data generated from this study will form the baseline for further study to other researchers.

Scope and Delimitation

This study is delimited to 3 selected faculties in Bayero University Kano.

Literature Review

Before the industrial revolution in the 15th century, tourism had begun with non-formal recreational activities such as storytelling, wrestling, swimming and indoor games among the ancient people and grew to the level of creating leisure time, annual holiday, transport to place of events, involvement in spas centres for natural curative and

healing activities and movement to the coasts which led to the development of seaside resorts. Today, these has contributed positively to the economic growth, job creation, entrepreneurship enhancement and earning income for the society. It also enhance conservation and diffusion of culture through the maintenance of renewal of culture goods which disappear, being a supporter of education through the provision of knowledge and information to tourist who wish to experience the particular national and cultural value and history of the place they are visiting. It contributes to physical wellbeing of an individual through recreation. Tourism can be classified into eco-tourism, geo-tourism, film, cultural, business, educational, religion etc.

Eco-tourism, Ayodele (2010) stated that ecotourism is a tourism that involves travelling to relatively undistributed (an undistributed place, is a peaceful place that has not been affected by changes that have happened in other place) natural areas with the objective of admiring, studying and enjoying the scenery and its wild plants and animals as well as any cultural features found there. Ecotourism has been espoused widely as a tool for commercial profit, community development and environmental conversation (UNEP/WTO, 2012).

Geo-tourism: is a form of natural area tourism that specifically focuses on geology and landscape. It promotes tourism to geo-sites and the conservation of geo-diversity and an understanding of earth sciences through appreciation and learning. This is achieved through independent visits to geological features, use of geo-trails and view point, guided tours, goe-activities and patronage of geo-site visitor centres. (Newsome and Dowling. 2010)

Film tourism: Chi-chu Samuel (2012) stated that a new tourism product named film tourism was born in the late 1980s. That since the phenomena, it continue to be an avenue for income earning. That it is a system of tourism where people move from their own destination to another place to watch film or television programs and pay. The visitors experience a new thing while the host community benefit directly or indirectly from the visitors.

Religious tourism: according to Marguda (2010), religious tourism involves all activities that motivate the faithful to undertake organized journeys to sacred sites and locations. This sacred sites or shrines may be within their country or outside their geographic region. Such as annual pilgrimage to Macca and Jerusalem that both Christians and Muslims perform. He further explain that in Nigeria for example, some people visits shrines like Osun Osogbo shrine as belief to be goddess of fertility, Sango, the god of thunder and lighting, the Hubbare (Shehu Usman Dan Fodio's Tomb) in Sokoto among social annual rituals performed by the followers of the traditional belief.

Safari tourism: is an individual form of travel for the purpose of enjoying nature and wildlife while moving along through wild environment. Roth and Merz (2013) reported

that safari is any commercially organized individual group or wildlife tours in Africa, aimed at the discovery, study and enjoyment of wildlife nature in general. Hiyew and Jarvis cited in Yale (2010) highlighted that safari is holidays which were mainly an African product with focus parks of Kenya, Tanzania and South Africa. But today, Safari has more move beyond these countries to others part of Africa like Zambia, Zimbabwe, and Botswana even to Asia example, India and other countries with plentiful indigenous wildlife. Safari is a holidays that take people from the area of staying to a destination for watching of wildlife from safari vehicle, usually a land-rover or minibus, often painted with Zebra stripes for camouflage. Heyes and Jarvis said that safari is an exciting journey, leaving the cities and towns far behind and traveling in African bush, full of wild animals living proud and free in their natural habitat, while you position yourself perfectly to capture some wild with your camera.

Agritourism: Blacka (2011) stated that agriculture tourism can contributes to economy because it allows farm operation to increase income through a variety of services initiatives such as farm demonstrations, harvest festivals, pick-your-own crop farm harvest, bed and breakfast, campgrounds, crop mazes, and a host of other products and services.

Culture: culture tourism embodies such activities as organized visit to historical sites, visiting others culture and people. Tosic and Lazarevic (2010) pointed out that cultural tourism is viewed; from the *economic point* as a placement of culture on the market with culture and artistic product, that has cultural and economic value. From organizational point, the integrations between two sectors; culture and tourism, which merge with a view to forming a mutual product? From *cultural point*, it is a promotion of revived cultural goods and the landscape of a town that will be etched on tourists' minds. From *educational point*, as a journey full of longing to explore, get to know and learn something new about national or a country values of the region tourists are visiting. From a viewpoint of *marketing and PR*, cultural tourism is the managing of the reputation of a place, region or a country based on the cultural goods and landscapes.

Sinha (2011) describe tourism information as that information that potential tourist to access the destination of interest. It is any literatures or published materials that enable a tourist to have insight information about attractions and destinations, various practices of the local people at the destination, taxes and tripping, postal services, shop hours and restaurants. He further stated that, sources of information on tourism are pamphlets, leaflets, DVDs, journals, Newspapers, geographical and tourism maps, monographs images, audio recordings, Bulletins, Brochures, flyers, travel guides, internets, television and documentaries, Radio and other bits of information materials on attractions of the areas to be visited, with some travel checklist including videos and web sites. However, tourism information itself is that information on areas of tourism

that an individual is interested on for example; Kurent (2011) said that tourism information can be sought from internet, in the library, video, friends and colleagues, documentaries from television (e.g) national geography wildlife, telephone call, travel guide such as (the world heritage), national park news, bulletins, leaflets, flyers from hospitalities (e.g. hotels), tourism maps and signboards, newspapers, brochures, magazines, journals and directories. Scarrott (2011) reported that sources of tourism information includes journals and periodicals, Newspapers, brochures, hotel flyers, magazines, library bibliographies and catalogues, abstracts, indexes, thesis and dissertation, directories and internet.

Methodology

Survey research method was adopted for the study. The population of this study consists of 600 academic staff of Bayero University, Kano, the subject of the study were one hundred and eight nine (189) respondents Stratified sampling techniques were used in selecting 189 (30%) respondents from the 10 faculties. In this method the researchers observed that the ten (10) faculties of the universities that formed the strata and 30% of the population were selected with 18 respondents from each stratum. A questionnaires was used in data collection for this research, close-ended questionnaire was design and used for the study.

The instrument for this study was validated by two lecturers in the department of geography of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and their suggestions were used to improve and produced the final copies of the instrument. Pre-test and post-test of the instrument was done with 20 academic staff in the department of computer science, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. All the (20) fill and completed questionnaire were retrieved and analysed using Cronbach at alpha coefficient level of significance at 0.05 Descriptive statistics of frequency distribution of simple percentages were used in the analysis

Research question one: What are the types of tourism information available to academic staff?

Table 1: The percentage analysis on type of tourism information

S/N	Types of Tourism Information	Responses		
		Available (2)	Not Available(3)	Total (1)
1.	Information on leisure and recreation	32 (19.0)	136 (77.3)	168
2.	Sports and games	97 (57.7)	71 (42.3)	168
3.	Tour operation and transport	35 (20.8)	133 (75.6)	168
4.	Spas and planetarium	13 (7.7)	155 (92.3)	168
5.	National park and wildlife	59 (35.1)	109 (64.9)	168
6.	Hotel and catering	59 (35.1)	109 (64.9)	168
7.	Arts festival	51 (30.4)	117 (69.6)	168
8.	Amusement park/fun fair	31 (18.5)	137 (81.5)	168
9.	Road side resorts	26 (15.5)	142 (80.6)	168
10.	Cultural heritages	111 (66.1)	57 (33.9)	168
11.	Wax work	15 (8.9)	153 (91.1)	168
12.	Museum/monumental centres	62 (36.9)	106 (63.1)	168
13.	Beaches and waters falls	26 (15.5)	142 (84.5)	168
14.	Picnics and fountains	34 (20.2)	134 (79.8)	168

Table 1 above shows available information on tourism for the academics. Information on cultural heritage has the highest scores with 111(66.1%) of the respondents this is likely due to role culture plays in the life of an African man, this findings tend to disagree with that of the Europeans Travel commission (2011) which observes that cultural tourism suffers a general unawareness of potential and use and enjoyment due to lack of accessibility. Perhaps their submission is based on Europeans setting. The need for man to understand culture and document tends to make information on it easily available.

Research question two: What are the means of accessing tourism information by academic staff?

Table 2: The summary of sources of tourism information among the academics staff
access to Tourism Information

Means of access	Frequency	Percentage
Internet	140	83.3
Video clips	39	23.2
Phone call	29	23.4
Travel websites	28	16.7
Leaflets	43	26.5
Brochures	43	26.5
Colleagues/friends/families	65	37.7
Telex	6	3.6

Table 2 above shows respondent access to tourism information. The responses of the respondents indicated that internet has the highest with 140(83.3%) as major means of accessing tourism information; this is due to the availability of mobile network as academics can easily browse with their mobile communication devices. This is in line with Scarott (2011) who said that internet can allow users to visually tour and visit tourism sites in real term. Colleagues and friends came second with 56(38.7%). In Africa one of the easiest ways to pass information across is through personal contact and this can be between colleagues, friends or family. Through, this is now been taken over through the net as each individual can now access information from the web easily as all one needs is just the knowledge. Telex has the lowest responses with 6 (3.6%) as this is been wipe out by the electronic media. The internet and mobile network have now hence people are moving away from the old of communication towards the modern ways like mobile phones, internet, text and many more.

These questions were further raised from research question two aimed at determining the importance of having access to tourism information among the academics of Bayero University, Kano.

Table 3: Present the summary of importance of accessing tourism information

Importance of having access to tourism information	A	IND	D
Having access to tourism information enables you to participate in tourism activities	95(56.5)	24(14.3)	49(29.2)
Access to tourism information enables you plan itinerary	116(69.1)	11(6.5)	42(29.4)
Access to tourism information gives you the choice to choose your destination before embarking on the trip	94(54.9)	11(6.5)	63(38.6)

Key: A= Agree, IND= Indifference D= Disagree

Table 3 shows the importance of having access to tourism information. From the table, it revealed that having access to tourism information arouse academics interest to participate in tourism activities with responses scores of 95(56.6%) agreed, 49 (29.2) disagree, 24(14.3) indifferent. Having access to tourism information enables the academics to choose destination to be visited, to plan and develop interest to participate on the activities. The implication is that when an individual have access to information and utilizes it, he/she has become inform and better understand that will help an

individual to develop interest on that thing. Furthermore, if academics have access and use information on tourism, they may have interest to participate and moreover plan against the trip.

Research question three: What are source of tourism information among the academics staff?

Table 4: Present summary of sources of tourism information among the academics staff

Sources	Rep. Freq	(%)	Sources	Rep. Freq	(%)
Internet	107	63.7	Maps	90	51.5
Colleagues/friends and family	92	54.8	Travel agencies	89	52.9
Tourism documentaries	86	51.2	Transportation/Cruise	61	36.3
Newspapers/ magazines	85	50.6	Television	33	19.6
Tourism information sites	80	47.6	Telex	7	8.6
National geography wild	67	39.9	Train	2	1.5
Bibliographies on tourism	57	33.9			
Indexes/ abstracts	52	31.0			
Library catalogues	51	30.4			
Phone call	46	27.4			
Travel websites	43	25.6			
Video clips	43	25.6			
Brochures	43	25.6			
Leaflets	24	14.3			
Tour guides	24	14.3			

Table 4 show internet 107 (63.7%) followed by colleagues/friends and family with 92 (54.8%), while train ranked the lowest with 2 (1.5%) respectively. From this result, revealed that Internet plays major role in every man’s life. It is a source of information for both remote accesses, this is in line with O’Connor (2011), Lucey (2005) and Bhatia (2011) who observed that internet today cater for travel activities of all kinds ranging from virtual sightseeing and offering detailed information on travel sites and it allow users to plan their own itinerary, make travel reservation online and travel dairies. Internet has revolutionized the world and it has shaped men’s daily lives as Scoratt (2011) rightly said, internet provides remote access to information at a finger tips.

Research question four: What are the challenges faced by the academics staff?

Table 4: Present the summary of challenges in accessing tourism information

Challenges	SA	A	IND	DA	SD
Most of tourism outlets/ sectors have not viable websites to locate them	14 (8.3)	67 (39.9)	32 (13.7)	61 (36.3)	3 (1.8)
Library staff discouraged access	30 (17.9)	8 (4.8)	56 (33.3)	60 (35.7)	14 (8.8)
Most of the tourism owned internet sites are not accessible or not interfaced friendly	17 (9.7)	24 (14.3)	40 (23.8)	54 (32.1)	33 (19.6)
Poor infrastructure like power, telephone, postal services hamper you from accessing tourism information	68 (40.5)	68 (40.5)	16 (9.5)	12 (32.1)	4 (2.4)
Poor knowledge of the organization of library resources	41 (24.2)	48 (28.7)	8 (4.8)	48 (28.4)	23 (13.7)
Lack of parents of library within your locality	10 (5.9)	30 (17.9)	14 (8.0)	60 (35.7)	54 (32.5)
Poor arrangement of library resources	48 (28.7)	46 (27.0)	27 (16.2)	37 (22.2)	10 (5.9)
Do you agree that some of the academics lack that knowledge of internet surfing on how to locate the needed information on tourism	47 (28.0)	80 (47.6)	21 (12.5)	11 (6.5)	9 (5.4)
Lack of interest on tourism information	46 (27.4)	65 (38.9)	8 (4.5)	23 (13.7)	26 (15.5)
Low knowledge on how to approach and search for information tourism in library	14 (8.5)	6 (3.6)	3 (1.8)	78 (46.5)	67 (39.7)

Table 4 shows 67 (39.9%) of the respondents agrees that most of the tourism outlets/sectors did not have viable website to locate them. Furthermore 80 (47.6%) of the respondents agreed that some of the academic lack the knowledge of internet surfing on how to locate the needed information on tourism, 68(40.5%) of the respondents agreed to poor infrastructure as the hindrances to tourism information access, 65 (38.9%) indicated lack of interest.

While library staff discourages access 60 (35.7) were strongly disagreed. However, lack of parents of library within locality ranked the lowest with 10 (5.9%) strongly disagreed, this implies that hindrances to information on tourism poor infrastructures and lack of interest by the academic

Summary of findings

- Types of tourism information available in the University are information on culture and festival, sport and games, leisure and recreation, museum, hotel and catering.
- The means of accessing tourism information are internet, television, documentaries, video clips, colleagues, family and Libraries.
- The sources of tourism information are internet, Library, Friends/colleagues and family, travel agencies, transport industries, Newspaper and magazines, brochures and exhibition.
- The challenges academic staff faced in accessing tourism information lack of awareness, tourism interest and poor infrastructure

Conclusion

From the findings of this study, it was concluded that accessibility that to tourism information by academic staff is very necessary because, tourism has been a social therapy to stress and boredom. Hence academics are vulnerable to fatigue and stress due to the work overload. The benefit of tourism to human is enormous, when one participate in tourism through recreation (physical exercises), it makes one look agile, healthy, mental alert, always look youthful, it low body fats and weight, reduce blood sugar level in body system (systolic blood pressure (BP) to pave way for efficient functioning of heart and lungs and it makes one intellectually balance and cohesive to manage it time well. From this study, it can be deduced that it is necessary for everybody academics not left out to have access to tourism information, hence it will help individual to develop maintain optimal level of health, increase physical work capability and decrease early disability and sudden death.

Recommendations

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Information on all types of tourism should be provided and make available for academics and public access.
2. All necessary means of accessing information on tourism should be inculcated in the library for easy accessibility.
3. Material on tourism should be provides in Libraries with internet services to enable academics have access to tourism information.

4. Necessary infrastructure should be provided and make available in order to enhance information accesses.
5. Library staff should be equipped with all desire training to meet needs of users in term of information service provision.

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